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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable, “Report on orbital angular momentum resolved EELS of metallic nanostructures in TEM” has the aim of defining an appropriate framework for the simulation of energy loss experiments on plasmonic nanosystems, resolved in orbital angular momentum (OAM), where the inelastically scattered electrons are dispersed both in energy and in OAM: as we demonstrate in the following Chapters, these combined dispersions give access to information about the plasmonic excitations characterizing the metallic nanostructure not available in conventional STEM-EELS experiments.

The current document is structured as a report to improve its readability, however a large part of the results presented here have been published in M. Zanfrognini *et al.*, *ACS Photonics* 2019, **6**, 620-627.

Finally, the first experimental characterization of the plasmonic nanostructures which will be adopted for future experiments are also reported.

Chapter 1. We define the experimental set up together with the experimental observables, and we outline a procedure by which they can be numerically computed. Further, we also discuss how these functions can be modified to include experimental details, like the broadening in energy of the electron beam and the finite resolution of the OAM spectrometer.

Chapter 2. We describe the application of OAM resolved EELS in the analysis of plasmon resonances of metallic nanostructures which are azimuthally symmetric, i.e. invariant under an arbitrary rotation around the TEM optical axis.

Chapter 3. We apply OAM resolved EELS to the case of morphed nanostructures, to point out the capability of this approach of revealing how plasmon modes of a given nanostructure hybridize once its geometrical shape is slightly morphed.

Chapter 4. We illustrate the potential application of this technique to resolve the contributes to the energy loss due to quasi degenerate modes.

Chapter 5. We describe the potential application of this approach to the analysis of chiral plasmonic nanostructures in transmission electron microscopy. Finally we propose a composed nanostructure, which is expected to provide giant dichroic effect, making simpler a first clear experimental observation of this effect.

Chapter 6. We will describe briefly the fabrication of the plasmonic structure of some relevant structures.

Chapter 7. We present a first set of experimental data concerning the structure we plan to use in first experiments on OAM resolved EELS, and we present initial measurements on this plasmonic nanostructure through an electrostatic sorter.

1. GENERAL SURFACE PLASMON THEORY WITH OAM RESOLVED FINAL STATE

In conventional experiments for the analysis of plasmonic metallic nanostructures a focused electron beam is scanned on and closer the system of interest and for each position the energy spectrum of the transmitted electron beam is analyzed. In particular, the fraction of electrons having lost an energy E can be written (in quasi static approximation) as shown in Ref.[¹]

$$\Gamma(E, R_0) \propto \sum_i f_i(E) |\varepsilon_z^i(q, R_0)|^2$$

where the sum is performed over the plasmonic modes of the nanostructure, $f_i(E)$ are functions that, for each i are peaked at the excitation energy of that i^{th} mode, and $\varepsilon_z^i(q, R_0)$ provides the Fourier transform of the z component of the electric field associated to the i^{th} resonance, computed in the point R_0 in which the beam is focused and at the spatial frequency $q = \frac{E}{\hbar v}$, with v the electron speed. It is simple to realize that in this way it is possible to obtain a spatial mapping of the electric fields associated to each plasmon resonance of the metallic nanostructure, with nanometric spatial resolution. As already pointed out in the literature, for example by Guzzinati *et al.* [²], such an approach fails once we want for example to distinguish modes having similar energies and spatial distribution; further, it does not provide information about the chirality of plasmonic fields.

In these experiments, the only degree of freedom effectively probed by the electron beam interacting with the nanoparticle is the energy it loses as a function of the point in which the probe is focused. Differently, in OAM resolved EELS, we exploit the capability of measuring the electron orbital angular momentum (OAM) along the TEM optical axis, recently demonstrated experimentally [³], to evaluate both the energy and the OAM spectrum of the inelastically scattered beam.

From the mathematical point of view, we assume the electron beam before interacting with the sample in a quantum mechanical state $|i\rangle$, with well defined energy E_0 : the electron nanoparticle interaction can be modeled by an interaction Hamiltonian \hat{H}_{e-NP} which changes the quantum state of the electron, from $|i\rangle$ to $|f\rangle$.

The combined action of the energy spectrometer and of the OAM analyzer in the TEM column can be modeled through a projector operator given by $\hat{P}(\ell, E) = \sum_p |\ell, p, E\rangle \langle \ell, p, E|$, where $|\ell, p, E\rangle$ is a quantum mechanical state describing an electron with energy E and OAM along z equal to $\hbar\ell$, while p is a quantum number whose meaning will be clarified in the following. Therefore, the probability of the electron to be found in a state with OAM $\hbar\ell$ and energy E after the sample is given by

$$\Gamma_\ell(\Delta E) = \sum_p |\langle \ell, p, E | f \rangle|^2$$

which is effectively the quantity evaluated in OAM resolved EELS experiments on plasmonic nanoparticles.

From the experimental point of view this quantity can be measured through an experimental set up schematically reported in Figure 1.1. Two phase masks are inserted in the TEM column, after the sample plane, i.e. the Sorter 1 at the level of the Objective aperture and Sorter 2 in correspondence of the SAD aperture plane. It is important to

underline that Sorter1 is positioned in the front focal plane of Lens 1, which has in its back focal plane the Sorter 2 element; at the same time, Lens 2 has in its front focal plane the SAD aperture itself and in its back focal plane the aperture of the energy spectrometer. The role of Sorter 1 is to perform a log-polar coordinate transformation of the wave function, i.e. to map the azimuthal variation of phase of the electron along a Cartesian coordinate, while the action of Sorter 2 is to introduce the necessary corrections to the defects produced by the first phase element. To clarify this point, we assume an initial beam with orbital angular momentum along z equal to $\hbar\ell$: the action of the two sorters is to transform the initial circular phase into a linear phase along the in-plane y direction, which is transformed by Lens 2 into a spot centered in $y = \frac{f_2 L}{ak}$, (where k is the electron De Broglie wave vector) in the back focal plane of Lens 2. If this plane coincides with the aperture plane of the spectrometer, its role will be to disperse the electrons forming this spot in the perpendicular direction, according to their energies: in this way the OAM resolved EEL spectrum should be obtained through a CCD camera located at the end of the energy spectrometer. Because of the linearity of the overall experimental set up, in the case of a beam with more than one OAM components, in the back focal plane of Lens 2 we expect to observe a series of spots, one for each ℓ component, whose intensity ratios are equal to the relative weight of the contributes of the different OAM to the electron wave after the sample. In Figure 1.1 we present how a beam given by the superposition of two vortices, one with $\ell = +2$ and one with $\ell = -2$ is transformed by the overall experimental set up.

Figure 1.1 Schematic description of the electron optics in the TEM column, necessary to measure OAM resolved EELS spectra. Looking at the bottom right of this image, we can see the resulting double dispersed signal in orthogonal directions, i.e. in energy and in OAM.

Having defined the general features of the experimental set up, we now focus on the numerical calculation of the OAM resolved loss function $\Gamma_\ell(\Delta E)$. Because of the definition given before, it is immediate to demonstrate that such function is proportional to the transition probability from the initial electronic state (before interaction) to a state with OAM $\hbar\ell$ and energy $E_0 - \Delta E$, in single scattering approximation.

We provide now a brief description about how it is possible to simulate OAM resolved electron energy loss spectra. We start by describing the interaction between a probe electron in \vec{r} and the charge density $\rho(\vec{r}')$ of the nanostructure through the following interaction Hamiltonian,

$$\widehat{H}' = - \int e \frac{\rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d^3r' \quad (1.1)$$

where the integration is performed over the nanoparticle's volume, and ℓ is the charge of the electron. For a weak interaction, in first order approximation, the transition probability (Γ) from an initial electronic state $|i\rangle$ (with energy E_0) to a final state $|f\rangle$, with OAM value of $\ell\hbar$ can be computed using Fermi's golden rule, i.e.

$$\Gamma \propto \sum_{f,n} \left| \int \int d\vec{r} d\vec{r}' \frac{\Psi_f^*(\vec{r}) \Psi_i(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} \langle n | \rho(\vec{r}') | 0 \rangle \right|^2 \delta(E_f - E_0 + \varepsilon_n - \varepsilon_0). \quad (2.1)$$

Here, the OAM is defined along the probe electron's direction of propagation, i.e., the TEM optical axis (taken to be the z-axis), and $|0\rangle$ and $|n\rangle$ are, respectively, the ground state of the nanoparticle (with energy ε_0) and its n^{th} excited state. Exploiting the definition of electronic susceptibility $\chi(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', E)$ given in [4], and references therein, and considering only transitions for the probing electron to states with energy $E_f = E_0 - E$, it is possible to write,

$$\Gamma_\ell(E) \propto \sum_f \int \int d\vec{r} d\vec{r}' \Psi_f^\ell(\vec{r}) \Psi_i^*(\vec{r}') \text{Im}(-W(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', E)) \Psi_f^{\ell*}(\vec{r}') \Psi_i(\vec{r}') \delta(E_f + E - E_0) \quad (3.1)$$

with $W(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', E)$ being the screened interaction between an electron in \vec{r} and one in \vec{r}' . Following the approach shown in [1], we can write such a function as,

$$W(\vec{r}, \vec{r}', E) = \sum_m g_m(E) \phi_m(\vec{r}) \phi_m(\vec{r}')^* \quad (4.1)$$

where $\phi_m(\vec{r})$ is the potential associated to the m^{th} surface plasmon resonance of the metallic nanostructure, and $g_m(E)$ is the so called spectral function.

In the paraxial approximation, we take,

$$\Psi_{in}(x, y, z; \vec{K}_m) = e^{iK_{in}^z z} \psi_{in}(x, y) \quad (5.1.1)$$

$$\Psi_f^\ell(x, y, z; \vec{K}_f) = e^{iK_f^z z} \psi_f^\ell(x, y) \quad (5.2.1)$$

where $\psi_{in}(x, y)$ ($\psi_f^\ell(x, y)$) denotes the initial (final) electronic wave function in a plane perpendicular to the optical axis, while \vec{K}_{in} and \vec{K}_f are the electron wavevectors before and after the scattering process. This approach is correct every time K_{in}^z and K_f^z are much larger than the projection of the wavevector perpendicular to the optical axis.

By substitution of (4.1), (5.1.1) and (5.2.1) in Eq. (3.1), using non recoil approximation [4], summing over all the possible K_f^z (exploiting the delta function in (3.1)) and performing the integration along z , we finally obtain the desired OAM resolved loss function,

$$\Gamma_\ell(E) \propto \sum_f \sum_m \text{Im}(-g_m(E)) \left| \iint dx dy \psi_f^\ell(x, y) \phi_m(x, y, q) \psi_i(x, y)^* \right|^2 \quad (6.1)$$

where while $\phi_m(x, y, q)$ is the Fourier transform along z of the potential $\phi_m(\vec{r})$ [5].

In the following calculations, we will assume $\psi_i(x, y)$ to be a Gaussian beam whose waist is comparable with the size of the plasmonic nanoparticles, while we will write the final electronic states $\psi_f^\ell(x, y)$ as[6] [7],

$$\psi_f(x, y) = J_{|\ell|}(k_f r) e^{i\ell\varphi} \quad (7.1)$$

in which $J_{|\ell|}(k_f r)$ is a Bessel function of the first kind of order ℓ , k_f is the transverse wavevector (i.e. the projection of the electron wavevector \vec{k}_f on the xy plane, perpendicular to the optical axis), and ℓ is the winding number: here the transverse wave vector K_f corresponds to the quantum number p introduced in the definition of the projector operator which models the action of the OAM and energy spectrometers. In this way, the sum over the index f appearing in Eq.(6.1) is now performed over an ensemble of such final states characterized by a fixed ℓ and with transverse wavevector k_f in the interval $[0, K_{Max}]$, where K_{Max} depends on the collection angle α of the detector as $\alpha = K_{Max}\lambda$, with λ corresponding to the electron's De Broglie wavelength.

Such an approach permits also to eventually include structured incoming electron beams: notice that our choice of using Gaussian beams with quite large beam waists is only associated with the possibility of exciting all the different plasmonic resonances of the nanostructure at the same time. In any case, our results are not dependent on the choice of using an effectively Gaussian electron beam profile; a plane wave-like illumination gives qualitatively the same results, changing only the relative intensities of the peaks related to different modes.

The spectral function $g_m(E)$ depends on both the geometry and the dielectric properties of the considered metallic nanostructure, and its imaginary part (with a minus sign) is maximized at the m^{th} surface plasmon resonance energy. The analytical form of the imaginary part of this function is analogous to the one provided in [1] by Boudarham and Kociak considering the metallic nanostructure embedded in a homogeneous medium with constant dielectric function and neglecting the contribution to the electron energy loss due to bulk excitations. Finally, $\phi_m(x, y, q)$ is the Fourier transform, along z , of the electric potential associated with the m^{th} plasmonic mode; such a quantity does not depend on the dielectric properties of the material but only on the geometry of the considered sample.

Within this approach, the surface plasmon oscillations are treated classically, i.e. by computing the plasmon response function solving Maxwell's equations in the non retarded approximation through the boundary element method [4][5], implemented in MNPBEM toolbox [8]. The electron dynamics, however, are studied quantum mechanically using Fermi's golden rule, as outlined above. In the adopted theory, we neglect the contribution to the electron energy loss due to bulk plasmon excitations of the metal as their energies are expected to be larger than those of the localized surface

plasmons of interest. We also suppose the nanostructure to be embedded in vacuum, neglecting in this way the effect of the substrate on which the structures are located. As reported by [9], the effect of the substrate is both to red shift the plasmon resonances and to increase the line widths of the plasmonic features, but the symmetry properties of the excitations, in which we are interested, are expected to be left unchanged by the substrate itself: anyway, in view of future experiments, the red shift of the plasmon resonances due to the substrate can be taken into account, at least partially, assuming the nanoparticle to be embedded in a medium with an effective dielectric function chosen to fit the observed excitation energies of the plasmonic excitations (see Figure 1.2).

As a final remark, we also point out that neglecting retardation effects should mainly give a blue-shift of the excitation energies [4Error! Bookmark not defined.], while leaving unchanged the symmetries of the modes which are the target of the proposed experiments. In any case, although we employ here for simplicity the quasi-static approximation throughout, future work should also address the case of the full Maxwell's equations where a modal decomposition into resonance modes could be performed.

Figure 1.2 Difference between the real configuration in experiments and the one which can be simulated within our model: practically, the nanostructure is assumed to be embedded in a homogeneous medium having an effective dielectric function. In the following it will be fixed to a constant, while in future experiments it will be chosen so to obtain energies in agreement with those observed experimentally.

Despite the (reasonable) performed approximations, this model gives us a simple expression (Eq.6.1) relating the electric potential associated to the plasmon resonances of the metallic nanostructure $\phi_m(x, y, q)$ to what is experimentally measured in OAM resolved EELS, i.e. the function $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ for different ℓ .

In reality, the limited instrumental resolution of the analysing system must be taken into account in order to obtain results which can be, in some way, compared with those found experimentally.

In order to show results closer to a realistic experiment, we have convolved the numerically obtained loss functions $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ with a Gaussian function keeping into account the broadening introduced by the experimental apparatus, i.e.

$$G(\ell, E) = \frac{-\ell^2}{e^{2\sigma_\ell^2}} \frac{-E^2}{e^{2\sigma_E^2}}$$

where $\sigma_\ell = \frac{\Delta\ell}{2.355}$ and $\sigma_E = \frac{\Delta E}{2.355}$; the quantity $\Delta\ell$ has been taken (in the following chapters) equal to $0.5 \hbar$, and this accounts for the broadening in the dispersion introduced by the

Sorter elements, while ΔE considers the non monochromaticity of the probing electron beam.

We underline here that the OAM is treated as a continuous variable, since the Sorters can transform a vortex with topological charge ℓ in a spot centered at coordinate $C\ell$, with a lateral extension equal to $C\Delta\ell$ (where C is a constant that depends on the sorter parameters and is assigned a value of unity for simplicity in the images presented below). An example of this convolution procedure is provided in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3 On the left, we plot an example of the un-convolved function $\Gamma_\ell(E)$. On the right the results obtained by the convolution process described in the text are shown: this is an example of a map we expect to evaluate experimentally, with dispersions in OAM and energy in orthogonal directions.

Finally, we provide a few details about how the numerical evaluation of the functions $\Gamma_\ell(E)$.

The functions implemented in the MNPBEM toolbox has been exploited to discretize the surface of the considered plasmonic nanoparticles (an example of how the surface of a nanoparticle is discretized is provided in Figure 1.4); we have then computed the surface charge distributions associated to the different plasmonic resonances of the nanostructure as

$$\int d\mathbf{s}' F(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') \sigma_m(\mathbf{s}') \xrightarrow{\text{discretization}} \sum_j \Delta s_j F(\mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{s}_j) \sigma_m(\mathbf{s}_j) = 2\pi\lambda_m \sigma_m(\mathbf{s}_i) \quad (8.1)$$

where \mathbf{s}_i is the position of the center of the i^{th} element in which the nanostructure surface has been discretized, while $\sigma_m(\mathbf{s}_j)$ indicates the surface charge distribution associated to mode m , and

$$F(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{s}') = \frac{-\mathbf{n}_s \cdot (\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}')}{|\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}'|^3}$$

being \mathbf{n}_s the normal vector to the surface of the nanostructure at \mathbf{s} : the sum appearing in Eq. 8.1 is performed on the nanostructure discretized surface elements. From this equation, it is simple to notice that computing the surface charge modes means solving a linear eigenvalue problem, which directly provides the eigencharges: notice that the corresponding eigenvalues determines the position in energy of the peaks for the

spectral functions defined in the main text. The quantities $\sigma_m(\mathbf{s}_j)$ and λ_m are computed through the MNPBEM toolbox. The potential associated to the resonance m , ϕ_m , can be written as

$$\phi_m(x, y, z) = \int \frac{\sigma_m(\mathbf{s}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{s}'|} d\mathbf{s}'$$

where the integral is again performed as a sum over the nanostructure surface elements. From this expression it is easy to compute the Fourier transform along z , i.e.

$$\phi_m(x, y, q) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dz e^{-iqz} \phi_m(x, y, z) = \int d\mathbf{s}' \sigma_m(\mathbf{s}') \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dz \frac{e^{-iqz}}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{s}'|}$$

which has been solved through the tabulated integral

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dz \frac{e^{ibz}}{\sqrt{a^2 + z^2}} = 2K_0(ab)$$

where K_0 is a modified Bessel function of second kind of order zero. In this way the function $\phi_m(x, y, q)$ appearing in Eq.6.1 is known, and the OAM resolved loss functions can be evaluated as a sum over the different plasmonic resonances.

Figure 1.4 Discretization of the surface of a nanodisk performed by the functions implemented in MNPBEM; the electric surface charge distributions of each plasmonic mode are computed at the points in the center of each surface element i , so they can be numerically treated as one dimensional arrays of length equal to the number of elements into which the total area has been divided.

2. THE EXAMPLE OF THE NANODISK

First examples of OAM resolved EELS are the analysis of plasmon resonances in metallic nanostructures which possesses azimuthal symmetry, i.e. they are invariant under rotation of an arbitrary angle around the TEM optical axis: these can be considered as simple proofs of concept of the capability of this technique to distinguish modes according to the spatial symmetry of their associated fields. As an example, we will focus here on the case of a silver metallic nanodisk, with diameter of 70 nm and thickness of 10 nm.

These nanostructures are characterized by plasmonic modes with a well defined azimuthal behavior, i.e. the Fourier transform along z (FT $_z$) of the m^{th} plasmon resonance can be written as

$$\phi_m(x, y, q) = f_m(r, q)e^{im\varphi} + f_{-m}(r, q)e^{-im\varphi} \quad (1.2)$$

so that the different plasmonic excitations will be identified by a unique "azimuthal" number m , while the functions $f_m(r, q)$ will determine the radial behavior of such potentials.

In Fig. 2.1 we present the spatial distributions of the electric charge associated to the first, lower energy, plasmonic edge modes (charge oscillation concentrated on the sample edge) and also the charge profile of the first breathing mode, i.e. an excitation in which the charge oscillation has its maximum in the center of the disk.

Figure 2.1 Surface charge distributions of the first lower energy plasmonic modes of a silver nanodisk with diameter of 70 nm and thickness of 10 nm. These resonances are classified as a) dipolar mode ($m=1$), b) quadrupolar mode ($m=2$), c) hexapolar mode ($m=3$) and d) breathing mode ($m=0$).

By direct substitution of Eq.1.2 in the expression of $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ given by Eq.6.1, writing the integral over x and y in planar polar coordinates and exploiting the simple relation

$$\int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi e^{i(\ell-m)\varphi} = 2\pi\delta_{\ell,m}$$

we immediately realize that for each $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ we expect a peak only at the energy of the plasmonic resonance with "azimuthal" number ℓ . Therefore, with a single measurement, we expect to distinguish plasmonic excitations both according to their symmetries (i.e.

their azimuthal trends) and to their energies, enabling their clear identification directly from the experimental point of view.

To confirm this reasoning, we have performed numerical calculations on the silver nanostructure described before (assumed surrounded by vacuum), using the dielectric function for Silver taken from Johnson^[10] and taking $\psi_i(x, y)$ as a Gaussian beam with beam waist of 35 nm, matching the transverse size of the disk: the results of these calculations are shown in Figure 2.2, where we show (in b) the behavior of the loss function in the interval of energies [2;4] eV, where the first plasmonic modes locate in energy.

As expected, for each OAM value, we have a peak at the energy of the plasmonic mode with the corresponding azimuthal symmetry. Therefore, the intense maximum observed in the spectrum obtained for $\ell = \pm 1$ corresponds to the dipolar edge mode (depicted in the inset), while the peaks found for $\Gamma_{\pm 2}$ and $\Gamma_{\pm 3}$ are respectively due to the quadrupolar and the hexapolar edge resonances of the nanodisk. As a last remark, the maximum observed for $\ell = 0$ is related to the breathing mode of the nanodisk ^[11], which is characterized by an eigenpotential not dependent on the variable φ .

Figure 2.2 a) Tilted view of the silver nanodisk. b) Simulated OAM-resolved EEL spectra for different OAM values (see legend). The surface charge distribution of each plasmonic mode is reported as an inset, where positive (negative) charge corresponds to blue (yellow) tone. c) 2D representation of the EEL spectra convoluted with a Gaussian function simulating the limited instrumental resolution ($\Delta E = 0.3 eV$ and $\Delta \ell = 0.5 \hbar$), according to the procedure outlined in Chapter 1.

In Figure 2.2c) we also show the results obtained convolving $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ with a Gaussian broadening in both energy and OAM: in this case the parameters ΔE and $\Delta \ell$ have been

respectively fixed to 0.3 eV and $0.5 \hbar$; it is simple to realize that despite a not very high resolution in energy, the peaks turn out to be clearly distinguishable, thanks to the dispersion in OAM.

The results shown above have been obtained integrating Eq.6.1 over k_f in the range $[0, K_{Max}]$, where K_{Max} has been taken equal to 0.4 nm^{-1} , which corresponds to a semi-collection angle $\alpha = K_{Max} \lambda \approx 1 \text{ mrad}$ for the OAM spectrometer.

The value of K_{Max} has been chosen looking at the behaviour of the function $C_\ell^m(k_f)$, which is defined as

$$C_\ell^m(k_f) = \left| \iint dx dy \psi_{k_f}^\ell(x, y) \phi_m(x, y, q) \psi_i(x, y)^* \right|^2$$

and is related to the OAM resolved loss function through the equation

$$\Gamma_\ell(E) \propto \sum_k \sum_m^{K_{Max}} \text{Im}(-g_m(E)) C_\ell^m(k_f)$$

i.e. it gives the strength of the contribution of the term with transverse wave vector k_f to the overall $\Gamma_\ell(E)$. In Figure 2.3 we display these functions $C_\ell^m(k_f)$ in the case of the nanodisk, assuming again a Gaussian beam with beam waist of 35 nm as incident probe. Because of the selection rules described in the main text, for a mode characterized by azimuthal number m only the functions $C_{\pm m}^m(k_f)$ will be different from zero for some k_f : so in the following we plot, as examples, the function C for the dipolar ($m=1$), the quadrupolar ($m=2$) and the hexapolar ($m=3$) modes as a function of k_f (each function is normalized to its maximum value).

Figure 2.3 Behavior of $C_{\pm m}^m(k_f)$ for the dipolar, quadrupolar and hexapolar modes of the nanodisk: all the functions have been normalized to their maximum value.

It is immediate to notice, looking at Figure 2.3 , that the choice $K_{Max} = 0.4 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ is correct because for larger values of k_f the different functions C are effectively negligible. This approach has been repeated for the different structures which will be considered in the following chapters to effectively control the validity of the chosen values of K_{Max} . We also underline that defining an appropriate value for K_{Max} is of extreme importance also from the experimental point of view, as it strongly influences the experimental signal to noise ratio: infact, by choosing too small angles we would lose part of the signal due to certain plasmon resonances, while taking too large collection angles would increase the experimental noise, as the integration would be performed also on regions where a very small fraction of the electrons inelastically scattered by the plasmon excitations effectively go.

With the example of the nanodisk, we can immediately realize the capability of this technique to recognize and distinguish plasmon resonances according to their spatial symmetries: we will show in the following chapters that its applicability is not limited to azimuthally symmetry nanostructures, but can be extended also to more complex systems.

This approach turns out to have several advantages with respect to the experiment recently proposed by Guzzinati and co-workers[2], who adopted a structured beam to excite the nanostructure and collected only on-axis inelastically scattered electrons in order to detect the electron energy loss due to the mode with spatial symmetry matching the one of the incoming wave: therefore, this experimental mode requires:

- different structured beams (and, therefore, different measurements) to access the whole plasmonic spectrum of a nanostructure;
- very long acquisition times, in order to increase the signal to noise ratio, which is normally rather poor as the chosen collection angles are of the order of few μrad , and so only a small fraction of the inelastically scattered electrons are effectively analyzed.

It is immediate to realize that the adoption of OAM resolved EELS can solve these problems: in fact the dispersion in OAM enables to distinguish the different modes according to their symmetries with a single measurement (as all the OAM contributions are measured at the same time, with experimental set up presented in Figure 1.1) and, as a very large fraction of the electrons scattered by the localized surface plasmons of the nanoparticle are collected by the OAM analyzer, the signal to noise ratio is expected to be strongly improved.

3. BREAKING THE AXIAL SYMMETRY

As pointed out in Chapter 2, for systems with axial symmetry, the surface plasmon modes are characterized by a well-defined azimuthal behaviour. Once this symmetry is slightly broken the surface charges characterizing the various resonances no longer exhibit the simple azimuthal distributions shown for example in Figure 2.1. In the following we will focus on the deformation of a metallic nanodisk into a nano-ellipse and into a nano-triangle: the analysis of how the plasmon resonances are modified has been already presented in the literature [12], but here we will demonstrate how OAM resolved EELS can offer a deeper understanding of the mode evolution under the morphing of the original nanostructure, providing information not directly available in conventional STEM-EELS experiments.

Once the axial symmetry is broken by deformation, the modes of the obtained nanostructure can be thought as obtained by the superposition of resonances (with different azimuthal numbers) of the original nanostructure: in other words, the morphing process introduces an hybridization of two resonances of the original nanodisk, giving rise an excitation characterized by electric potential

$$\phi_\alpha(x, y, q) \approx c_{m_1}^\alpha f_{\pm m_1}^{Disk}(r, q) e^{\pm i m_1 \varphi} + c_{m_2}^\alpha f_{\pm m_2}^{Disk}(r, q) e^{\pm i m_2 \varphi}$$

In this case, the mode α of the morphed nanostructure is understood as the mixing of the modes m_1 and m_2 of the original metallic nanodisk, weighted by the coefficients $c_{m_1}^\alpha$ and $c_{m_2}^\alpha$ which define the modal mixing.

If we now substitute Eq. 1.3 in the expression of the OAM resolved loss function $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ given in Eq.6 of Chapter 1, we expect to observe peaks at the same energy, for loss functions computed for different ℓ : more precisely, if the mode α is given by the hybridization of the resonances m_1 and m_2 of the nanodisk, we will expect peaks for $\Gamma_{\pm m_1}$ and $\Gamma_{\pm m_2}$ at the energy of this excitation, i.e. E_α . Therefore, through OAM resolved EELS we expect to understand which modes mix together once the original nanostructure is morphed, an information which cannot be accessed through conventional EELS experiments.

We start focusing on the case of a metallic nano-ellipse obtained from the disk (diameter $D = 70$ nm), by taking the major axis $a = D(1 + \varepsilon_x)$ and the minor one $b = D(1 + \varepsilon_y)$. We have chosen to fix the area of the ellipse surface equal to the one of the disk, so, imposing this condition we have $\varepsilon_y = -\frac{\varepsilon_x}{1 + \varepsilon_x}$: in the calculations presented below we have taken $\varepsilon_x = 1/5$: the results of the calculations are presented in Figure 3.1. Looking at the OAM resolved EEL spectra, we immediately notice that the two degenerate dipolar edge modes of the nanodisk split in energy and give very intense peaks for $\ell = \pm 1$. At the same time, it is simple to observe that the functions $\Gamma_{\mp 2}$ and Γ_0 have a common peak at an energy of 2.975 eV; however, $\Gamma_{\mp 2}$ has a maximum at 3.05 eV not observable in the trend of Γ_0 .

Considering the reasoning exposed before, this effect can be justified by assuming that the two degenerate quadrupolar edge modes of the nanodisk separate in energy and the lower energy one mixes with the breathing mode: this common peak for $\Gamma_{\mp 2}$ and Γ_0 at the

same energy can be considered as an experimental demonstration of this mode hybridization.

To confirm this hypothesis, we have performed an OAM decomposition of the modes of the nano-ellipse. More clearly, let's write the FTz of the potential associated to a plasmon resonance α , computed at $q = \frac{E_\alpha}{\hbar v}$ as (v is the incident electron velocity)

$$\phi_\alpha(x, y; q) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} dk c_m(k, q) J_m(kr) e^{im\varphi} \quad (1.3)$$

Figure 3.1 a) Tilted view of the Ag elliptical nanodisk. b) Simulated OAM-resolved EEL spectra for different OAM values (see legend). The surface charge distribution of each plasmonic mode is reported as insets. c) 2D representation of the EEL spectra convoluted with a Gaussian function simulating the limited instrumental resolution ($\Delta E=0.3\text{eV}$ and $\Delta l=0.5\hbar$): notice a common strong intensity at about 3.0 eV for both $l=\pm 2$ and $l=0$, pointing out the hybridization of the quadrupolar and the breathing modes of the nanodisk.

i.e. we have developed such potential on the set of functions $\{J_m(kr)e^{im\varphi}\}$: the value of the coefficient $c_m(k, q)$ measures the importance of the term $J_m(kr)e^{im\varphi}$ for given k and m to the overall potential V_α . By multiplying Eq. 1.3 on both sides for $e^{-im_1\varphi}$ and integrating between 0 and 2π we find

$$\int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \phi_\alpha(x, y; q) e^{-im_1\varphi} = 2\pi \int_0^{\infty} dk c_{m_1}(k, q) J_{m_1}(kr) \quad (2.3)$$

where we have used $\int_0^{2\pi} e^{i(m-m_1)\varphi} d\varphi = 2\pi\delta_{m,m_1}$.

By multiplying both sides of Eq. 2.3 for $J_{m_1}(k'r)r$, integrating over r between 0 and ∞ and remembering the property

$$\int_0^{\infty} dr J_{m_1}(k'r)r J_{m_1}(kr) = \delta(k - k')/k$$

we find

$$c_{m_1}(k', q) = \frac{k}{2\pi} \int_0^{\infty} dr r J_{m_1}(k'r) \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi \phi_{\alpha}(x, y; q) e^{-im_1\varphi}$$

As we are mainly interested in the contribute of the term defined by the azimuthal number m to the potential ϕ , we can define a quantity equal to

$$C_{m_1}(q) \equiv \frac{\left| \int_0^{K_{Max}} c_{m_1}(k', q) dk' \right|^2}{\sum_m \left| \int_0^{K_{Max}} c_m(k', q) dk' \right|^2} \quad (3.3)$$

which is a quantity that gives information about the importance of the term characterized by the azimuthal number m_1 to the overall series in Eq. 1.3.

These coefficients have been obtained from the potential $\phi_{\alpha}(x, y; q)$ computed from BEM calculations (see Chapter 1), while the integral have been computed numerically approximating the integration over r with an integral between 0 and a certain r_{max} , which has been taken much larger than the characteristic dimension of the nanostructure.

In Figure 3.2 we show the values of the coefficients C_m in the case of the nanoellipse considered in Figure 3.1, for the modes giving the main peaks in the OAM resolved loss functions computed for different ℓ .

Figure 3.2 Calculation of the coefficient C_m (defined in Eq.3.3) for the plasmon resonances giving the main peaks for the OAM resolved loss functions, computed for different values of ℓ . The insets represent the surface charges associated to each single plasmon excitation, with the corresponding energies.

This decomposition practically confirm our precedent intuition: in particular the mode at energy of 2.98 eV is given by the mixing of the two degenerate quadrupolar modes ($\ell=\pm 2$) with the breathing excitation ($\ell=0$), while the resonance at 3.05 eV has no breathing contribution, and so it can be understood as the superposition of the quadrupolar resonances. At the same time the two low energy modes, at energies respectively of 2.4 eV and 2.825 eV are understood as the hybridization of the dipolar modes of the metallic nanodisk, while the resonance at 3.2 eV is mainly due to the coupling of the hexapolar modes, with a very small contribution due to the dipolar resonances, which is expected to be difficult to be experimentally probed. This mode mixing picture is in good agreement with the results already reported in the literature [12].

In Figure 1.3c, we present the expected results of a real life experiment, performing the same convolution procedure outlined in the case of the nanodisk. Even if the two close

peaks for $\Gamma_{\mp 2}$ cannot be resolved as their separation is smaller than the assumed broadening in energy, it is immediate to notice that both the loss functions computed for $\ell = \pm 2$ and $\ell = 0$ have strong intensities at about 3.0 eV, signaling the mode mixing described before, even with a non-ideal experimental set up.

A similar analysis has been also carried out once the nanodisk is morphed into a quasi nanotriangle.

Again, this case has been reported in [12], where it has been suggested that the lower energy resonances of the quasi nanotriangle can be understood as obtained by the hybridization of the dipolar and quadrupolar modes of the nanodisk. This point has been confirmed morphing a silver nanodisk (in this case with diameter of 100 nm) through the relation

$$R(\varphi) = (1 - \varepsilon)R_{tri}(\varphi) + \varepsilon R_{Disk}$$

where ε is the deformation parameter (in the range $[0,1]$), R_{Disk} is the disk radius, $R_{tri}(\varphi)$ is the contour of the obtained morphed structure and $R_{tri}(\varphi)$ is the border of the triangle one could obtain setting ε to zero: with this definition the closer ε is to 1 the smaller will be the deformation.

In Figure 3.3 we show the OAM resolved loss functions evaluated for $\ell = \pm 1$ and $\ell = \pm 2$, taking the deformation parameter equal to 0.5: it is simple to observe that both the loss functions are peaked at the same energies, pointing out the mixing among dipolar and quadrupolar modes of the metallic nanodisks in these two resonances of the morphed nanostructure.

Figure 3.3 OAM resolved loss functions computed for $\ell=\pm 1$ and $\ell=\pm 2$ for the nanostructure shown in the inset. A Gaussian beam with beam waist of 50 nm and positioned in the center of this nanostructure is taken as incident beam. Notice the two modes respectively at about 2.05 eV and 2.57 eV turn out to be given by the mixing of the quadrupolar and the dipolar resonances of the nanodisk, as both $\Gamma_{\pm 1}$ and $\Gamma_{\pm 2}$ are peaked at this energies.

If we now consider the ratio $R_{12} = \frac{\Gamma_1}{\Gamma_2}$ evaluated in correspondence of the energy of the second mode (i.e. the one at 2.57 eV), it is possible to demonstrate starting from Eq.6.1

and by substitution of expression of the potential given at the beginning of this chapter (taking $m_1 = 1$ and $m_2 = 2$)

$$R_{12} \propto \frac{|c_1|^2}{|c_2|^2}$$

where c_1 (c_2) denotes the strength of the contribute of the nanodisk dipolar (quadrupolar) mode to the resonance of the morphed structure at energy of 2.57 eV. In Figure 3.4 we show the trend of such a function computed for different values of the deformation parameter: it is clear that the more ε is closer to one the more such a mode assumes a purely quadrupolar nature, and it becomes coincident with the $m = 2$ resonance of the nanodisk.

Figure 3.4 Behaviour of the ratio R_{12} defined in the main text (and evaluated at the energy of the mode at 2.57 eV in Figure 3.3) as a function of the deformation parameter. In all the calculations the features of the incoming wavefunction have been kept fixed to the ones adopted before for the case $\varepsilon = 0.5$. Notice that the more the nanostructure becomes closer to the nanodisk ($\varepsilon \rightarrow 1$) the more this resonance acquires a purely quadrupolar character, as it becomes coincident with the $m = 2$ resonance of the nanodisk

This last result, which can be repeated for the different modes of a given morphed plasmonic nanostructure highlights the capability of OAM resolved EELS to clarify the way in which different modes mix together once the original nanostructure is deformed: in particular, comparing different nanostructures, it could be possible to directly access experimentally the degree of mixing of the different modes, looking at the values of the ratio R_{12} .

4. SEARCHING FOR HIGH ORDER OAM SIGNATURE

In this chapter we underline the possible adoption of this technique to resolve the contributions to the electron energy loss due to plasmonic excitations which are almost degenerate in energy, thanks to the dispersion in OAM of the inelastically scattered electron.

To clarify this point, we firstly focus on the analysis of a plasmonic metamolecule composed of four identical elliptical nanodisks, each one having major axis, minor axis and height measuring 120 nm, 60 nm and 10 nm, respectively. The nanoparticles are disposed along the 160 nm long sides of a square resulting in a minimum distance between them of 21 nm, and they are illuminated with a Gaussian beam with a large beam waist (300 nm), centered in the middle of the square. We display the results of the calculations performed on such a system in Figure 4.1

Figure 4.1 a) Top view of the plasmonic molecule composed of four identical Ag elliptical nanodisk. b) Simulated OAM-resolved EEL spectra for different OAM values (see legend). The surface charge distribution of each plasmonic mode is reported as insets. c) 2D representation of the EEL spectra convoluted with a Gaussian function simulating the limited instrumental resolution ($\Delta E = 0.3eV$ and $\Delta l = 0.5\hbar$).

To have a better understanding of the calculated OAM resolved EEL spectra, it is important to understand the spatial features of the potentials associated to the first three plasmonic modes of this complex nanostructure. These are presented in Figure 4.2, together with the OAM decomposition of the potentials performed according to the procedure outlined in the precedent chapter. We immediately notice that the mode at 2.02 eV (Fig. 4.2a) is characterized by very strong $l = \pm 4$ components and so it is

expected to give rise to peaks for $\Gamma_{\mp 4}$, as we effectively notice looking at the light blue curve shown in Fig. 4.1b.

Analogously, the spatial profile of the electric potential associated to the resonance at 2.46 eV (Fig. 2.4c) changes sign four times, so it is associated to a potential with $\cos(2\varphi)$ or $\sin(2\varphi)$ azimuthal dependence: such a behaviour effectively justify the presence of peaks at this energy for $\Gamma_{\mp 2}$, in the

Figure 4.2 Calculation of the coefficients C_m for the modes of the plasmonic metamolecule shown in Figure 4.1: in the left column the profiles of $\phi_\alpha(x, y; q)$ for the first three resonances (in energy) are displayed.

curve the OAM resolved loss function presented in Figure 4.1b. More complex is, instead, the case of the plasmon peak at 2.28 eV (Figure 4.2b) as the φ dependence of the electrostatic potential associated to this mode cannot be simply deduced graphically: its complete modal decomposition suggests that this excitation is characterized by very intense contributions of the type $e^{\pm i\varphi}$ and $e^{\pm i3\varphi}$, which give intense peaks for $\Gamma_{\mp 1}$ and $\Gamma_{\mp 3}$ at the energy of this resonance (see Figure 4.1b).

Therefore, as the different modes are characterized by different azimuthal trends, they are expected to give maxima for different values of OAM, so that at fixed ℓ only a single mode (of these three) will be responsible for a maximum of Γ_ℓ . This separation of the modes according to their different azimuthal symmetries enables us to distinguish their contributions, even if their separation in energy is smaller than the resolution in energy experimentally available. To understand this point, we can look at Figure 1.4c, where the calculate OAM resolved EELS functions have been convolved by Gaussians representing the broadening in energy and OAM, due to the non ideality of the experimental apparatus. Fixing $\Delta E = 0.3eV$ and $\Delta\ell = 0.5\hbar$, we notice that the different resonances can be now resolved, despite their energetic separation is below the supposed ΔE .

Similar calculations have been performed for another plasmonic metamolecule, in this case formed by three silver elliptical nanodisks, (major axis of 100 nm, minor axis of 30 nm, height of 10 nm) located on the sides of a equilateral triangle (side length of 160 nm), as shown in Figure 4.3a. Also in this case we have adopted as incident probe an electron wavefunction extended over the whole composite nanostructure (beam waist of 300 nm) centred in the middle of the triangle and we have evaluated the OAM resolved loss functions for different ℓ : the results are presented in Figure 3.4b.

Figure 4.3 a) Top view of the plasmonic molecule composed of three identical Ag elliptical nanodisks. b) OAM resolved EEL spectra evaluated for $\ell = \pm 1$, $\ell = \pm 2$, $\ell = \pm 3$ and $\ell = \pm 4$ (i.e. the OAM terms giving the larger contributions to the overall electron loss): notice that the first mode has only peaks for $\ell = \pm 3$, while the second one has contributions for $\ell = \pm 1$, $\ell = \pm 2$ and $\ell = \pm 4$.

It is simple to understand that low energy mode gives a maximum only for $\ell = \pm 3$, while the second resonance is responsible for the peaks at $\ell = \pm 1$ and $\ell = \pm 2$ in this range of energy: in Figure 4.3b, only $\ell = \pm 1$, $\ell = \pm 2$, $\ell = \pm 3$ and $\ell = \pm 4$ are shown as these are the strongest Γ_ℓ in intensity in this range of energies. Therefore, also in this case these two resonances, which are close in energy, can be in principle resolved as they provide contributions to OAM resolved loss functions with different ℓ .

In order to rationalize the peaks observed in Figure 4.3b, we perform an OAM decomposition of these two modes, similar to the one presented in Figure 4.2: this is shown in Figure 4.4.

The potential associated to the lower energy mode is characterized by a six lobes profile, which produces large value for the decomposition coefficients evaluated for $\ell = \pm 3$, and so a maximum for the OAM resolved loss functions evaluated at these OAM. At the same time, the second mode is characterized by less simple azimuthal trend: in this case the OAM decomposition helps us to understand the presence of peaks for $\Gamma_{\mp 1}$ and $\Gamma_{\mp 2}$ in Figure 4.3b, and so to rationalize the computed OAM spectra.

In the last part of this chapter we want to present a possible experiment in which the sorting of the electrons in terms of their OAM, together with an appropriate choice of the incident electronic wavefunction, should enable to resolve nearly degenerate plasmonic modes, even if their associated potentials have not a well defined azimuthal behavior, as for example in the systems considered before.

We consider the case of a nanorods' tetramer, in which four identical silver rods (length of 100 nm and width of 20 nm) are supposed to be positioned one perpendicular to the other, to form a cross: the distance of the edge of each rod from the center of the cross is taken equal to 15 nm.

In this case, we will focus on the analysis of the first four modes of the structure, which can be understood as the hybridization of the dipolar modes of the four nanorods: in Figure 4.5a-d we present the charge distributions of these modes, noticing that the ones shown in b and c are characterized by almost the same charge distributions and by the same energies, so we will consider them as a unique excitation in the following. In the calculations presented below, we have

Figure 4.4 Calculation of the coefficients C_m for the modes of the plasmonic metamolecule shown in Figure 3.4a: in a) the mode at energy of 1.75 eV is considered, while in b) the one at 1.97 eV is analyzed. On the left column, in both cases, the profiles of $\phi_\alpha(x, y; q)$ for these resonances are displayed.

Figure 4.5 a)-d) Surface charge distributions of the first lower energy modes of a nanostructure made of four silver nanorods with length of 100 nm and transverse diameter of 20 nm. The overall structure is supposed to be embedded in an homogeneous background with $\epsilon = 1.8$. e) Orientation of the four-lobed function with respect to the four nanorods forming the cross: the blue tone indicates region where the wavefunction is negative, while red tone denotes zones in which the incident beam has positive values. The image is not in scale with respect to real distances.

chosen as incident beam a four lobed wavefunction (oriented with respect to the rods as shown in Figure 4.5 e) whose analytical formula is

$$\psi_i(x, y) = Cxye^{-\frac{(x^2+y^2)}{w^2}}$$

centered in the middle of the cross and with $w = 55$ nm. In the following we will index the modes shown in Figure 4.5 a-d with indexes $\alpha = 1, 2, 3, 4$ respectively. Starting from Eq.6.1 and substituting the profile of the incident beam we obtain

$$\Gamma_\ell(E) \propto \sum_{\alpha} \text{Im}[-g_{\alpha}(E)] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int dx \int dy J_{\ell}(k_f r) e^{i\ell\varphi} \phi_{\alpha}(x, y; q) Cxye^{-\frac{(x^2+y^2)}{w^2}} \right|^2 \quad (1.4)$$

Calling

$$f_{\alpha}(x, y, q) = \phi_{\alpha}(x, y; q) Cxye^{-\frac{(x^2+y^2)}{w^2}} \quad (2.4)$$

and substituting this in Eq.1.4 we find

$$\Gamma_\ell(E) \propto \sum_{\alpha} \text{Im}[-g_{\alpha}(E)] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int dx \int dy J_{\ell}(k_f r) e^{i\ell\varphi} f_{\alpha}(x, y, q) \right|^2$$

In Figure 4.6 we display the spatial profile of the functions $f_\alpha(x, y, q)$ computed for the three modes of interest.

Figure 4.6 Spatial behaviour of the product between an incident 4-lobed beam and the Fourier transform of the potentials associated to the first four plasmonic modes shown in Figure 5.4 a-d. In b) we present a unique plot for both the second and the third mode of the nanocross as they are effectively equal one to the other.

Looking at Figure 4.6a, it is possible to notice that the in-plane spatial behaviour of f_1 is characterized by two concentric rings, with altogether eight lobes on each of them: this suggests that this function can be reasonably approximated by a leading term given by

$$f_1(x, y, q) \approx h_4(r, q)e^{i4\varphi} + h_{-4}(r, q)e^{-i4\varphi}$$

so, once substituted in the expression of $\Gamma_\ell(E)$, it is simple to deduce that the loss functions for $\ell = \pm 4$ should be peaked at the energy of this resonance. f_2 and f_3 (both presented in Figure 6.4b) are still characterized by two-ring profile, but, in this case, with six lobes on each of them: this spatial profile should

give an intense maximum for $\Gamma_{\mp 3}(E)$ at the energy of these resonances, but, as the profiles of these lobes are not all the same (i.e. they have both different intensities and shapes), it is also reasonable to expect peaks for $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ with $\ell \neq \pm 3$. Finally, f_4 (displayed in Figure 4.6c) is characterized by an almost perfect four lobed distribution, which suggests the possibility of approximating such function with an expression similar to the one assumed for f_1 , but having exponentials of the type $e^{\pm i2\varphi}$; therefore, by substitution in $\Gamma_\ell(E)$ it is immediate to expect a peak associated to this excitation for $\ell = \pm 2$.

In Figure 4.7 we show the OAM resolved EEL spectra computed for the considered cross made of four silver nanorods described before: the predictions performed only on the basis of the symmetries of the functions f_α turn out to be in good agreement with the computed spectra; in fact the modes $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha = 4$ give only maxima respectively for $\ell = \pm 4$ and $\ell = \pm 2$, while the modes presented in Fig.4.6b are responsible for the

presence of peaks for $\ell = \pm 3$ (as expected) but also for $\ell = \pm 1$ and $\ell = \pm 5$, because of the modulation of the lobes characterizing the spatial profile of f_2 and f_3 .

Figure 4.7 OAM resolved EEL spectra for the structure shown in Figure 5.4, assuming as incident beam the four lobed function described in the main text with $w = 55$ nm, oriented with respect to the cross as reported in Figure 4.5e. Notice that in agreement with the spatial trends of the functions f_α shown in Figure 6.4, $\Gamma_{\mp 4}$ are peaked at the energy of mode $\alpha = 1$, $\Gamma_{\mp 2}$ at the energy of mode $\alpha = 3$, while the modes $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha = 3$ give maxima for $\Gamma_{\mp 3}$ as expected, but also for $\Gamma_{\mp 1}$ and $\Gamma_{\mp 5}$, because of the asymmetries between the different lobes in Figure 6.4b.

These results underline that each of these four different plasmon resonances give a maximum for a different loss function Γ_ℓ , and so no cases in which two peaks associated to two different modes are observed for the same OAM-resolved loss function, even if the potentials associated to the single resonances do not have a well defined azimuthal trend.

Such property has been obtained by adopting a peculiar incident probe (the four lobed beam), that, multiplied with the plasmonic potentials, provided functions f_α with the desired azimuthal symmetries. This approach requires the introduction in the TEM column of a further device to produce the structured incoming wave, but the result here presented for this nano-cross (which can be generalized to other nanostructures, working with different probes) suggests that, as different modes give maxima for functions with different OAM, they should become resolvable, also without the need of using electron incident beams with ΔE less than 0.1 eV. The only requirement is that the broadening in energy of the incoming beam should be sufficiently small to permit to keep separate the contributes to the electron energy loss, due to the plasmonic modes obtained by the hybridization of dipolar nanorods' modes from those of the modes given by the combination of higher order resonances: to have some numbers in mind, the

modes of the cross obtained combining quadrupolar profiles on the rods have energies equal to 2.4 eV, so at about 0.8 eV from the excitation of interest for us; therefore a $\Delta E \approx 0.4$ eV is expected to be enough to perform the presented experiment.

5. DICHOIC/CHIRAL STRUCTURES

In the precedent chapters we have shown how OAM resolved EEL spectroscopy can provide information about the symmetries of the potentials associated to the plasmonic modes of metallic nanostructures, in a plane xy perpendicular to the optical axis z of the electron microscope.

In reality, as we will demonstrate below, probing the OAM spectrum of the inelastically scattered electrons by localized surface plasmons can also give information about the mirror symmetry of the plasmonic potentials. $\phi_\alpha(x, y, z)$ with respect to a plane perpendicular to z . Let's consider the potential $\phi_\alpha(x, y, z)$ associated to the plasmonic resonance α of a certain nanostructure: as shown in Chapter 1, the OAM resolved loss function is dependent on

$$\phi_\alpha(x, y, q) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dz \phi_\alpha(x, y, z) e^{-iqz}$$

Now, let's assume that this potential is symmetric under mirror reflection with respect to the xy plane, i.e.

$$\phi_\alpha(x, y, z) = \phi_\alpha(x, y, -z) \quad (1.5)$$

By remembering that $\phi_\alpha(x, y, z)$ by definition, it is easy to demonstrate that (simply using the properties of one dimensional Fourier transform) $\phi_\alpha(x, y, q)$ is a real function too. Taking this into account, we suppose to rewrite the FTz of the potential as

$$\phi_\alpha(x, y, q) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{+\infty} f_m^\alpha(r, q) e^{im\varphi} \quad (2.5)$$

but, as $\phi_\alpha(x, y, q)$ is real $\phi_\alpha(x, y, q) = \phi_\alpha(x, y, q)^*$ so that

$$\sum_{m=-\infty}^{+\infty} f_m^\alpha(r, q) e^{im\varphi} = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{+\infty} f_m^{\alpha*}(r, q) e^{-im\varphi}$$

from which, by simple algebraic manipulations, it can be found $f_m^\alpha(r, q) = f_{-m}^{\alpha*}(r, q)$.

Let's now assume to take a plane wave as the incident wavefunction, so the function Γ_ℓ can be rewritten as (assuming as incident beam a plane wave)

$$\Gamma_\ell(E) \propto \sum_{\alpha} \text{Im}[-g_\alpha(E)] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int_0^{\infty} r dr J_{|\ell|}(k_f r) \sum_{m=-\infty}^{+\infty} f_m^\alpha(r, q) \int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi e^{i\varphi(\ell+m)} \right|^2 \quad (3.5)$$

Remembering, as usual,

$$\int_0^{2\pi} d\varphi e^{i\varphi(\ell+m)} = 2\pi \delta_{m, -\ell}$$

we obtain

$$\Gamma_{\ell}(E) \propto \sum_{\alpha} \text{Im}[-g_{\alpha}(E)] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int_0^{\infty} r dr J_{|\ell|}(k_f r) f_{-\ell}^{\alpha}(r, q) \right|^2 \quad (4.5)$$

Let's now focus on a certain mirror symmetric plasmonic mode, with energy E_{α} enough separate from the other excitations so that

$$\Gamma_{\ell}(E \approx E_{\alpha}) \propto \text{Im}[-g_{\alpha}(E_{\alpha})] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int_0^{\infty} r dr J_{|\ell|}(k_f r) f_{-\ell}^{\alpha}(r, q) \right|^2 \quad (5.5)$$

As $f_{\ell}^{\alpha}(r, q) = f_{-\ell}^{\alpha*}(r, q)$, we can write

$$\Gamma_{\ell}(E \approx E_{\alpha}) \propto \text{Im}[-g_{\alpha}(E_{\alpha})] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int_0^{\infty} r dr J_{|\ell|}(k_f r) f_{\ell}^{\alpha*}(r, q) \right|^2 \quad (6.5)$$

But the result of the integral in Eq.(6.5) is a complex number, whose modulus square is equal to the modulus square of its complex conjugate, i.e. we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{\ell}(E \approx E_{\alpha}) &\propto \text{Im}[-g_{\alpha}(E_{\alpha})] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int_0^{\infty} r dr J_{|\ell|}(k_f r) f_{\ell}^{\alpha*}(r, q) \right|^2 \\ &= \text{Im}[-g_{\alpha}(E_{\alpha})] \sum_{k_f} \left| \int_0^{\infty} r dr J_{|\ell|}(k_f r) f_{\ell}^{\alpha}(r, q) \right|^2 = \Gamma_{-\ell}(E \approx E_{\alpha}) \end{aligned}$$

which is equal to the OAM resolved loss function compute for the opposite OAM $-\ell$.

Therefore, through these simple steps, it is possible to demonstrate that for a plasmonic potential with mirror symmetry respect to the xy plane perpendicular to the optical axis, the loss functions Γ_{ℓ} and $\Gamma_{-\ell}$ are equal one to the other, at the energy of that plasmon excitation, in the case of an incident beam with zero topological charge (as the considered plane wave). It is clear that the above conclusions are valid up to when $f_{\ell}^{\alpha}(r, q) = f_{-\ell}^{\alpha*}(r, q)$ i.e. when the potential possesses mirror symmetry: once such property is missed, it is reasonable to expect the appearance of differences between the loss functions associated to $\pm\ell$.

To clarify this point we have considered the silver nanostructures shown in Figure 5.1, where their characteristic dimensions are also reported.

Figure 5.1 a) z-symmetric L shaped plasmonic nanostructure. b) Plasmonic nanostructure not symmetric under the operation $z \rightarrow -z$. Both the systems are made of silver and are assumed to be embedded in vacuum.

The structure presented in Figure 5.1b can be thought to be obtained from the one in Figure 5.1a by moving upwards (i.e. along z) one of the arms of the L shaped structure: the result is that the second system is not symmetric with respect to the operation $z \rightarrow -z$, differently from the original one.

In Figure 5.2 we present the OAM resolved loss spectra computed for $\ell = \pm 1$ for these two nanostructures, assuming the same probe in both cases, centered in correspondence of the two rods (this point is denoted by a red spot in Figure 5.2): here and in the remaining part of this Chapter we will focus on $\ell = \pm 1$ as the loss functions computed for this value of OAM are the most intense.

It is immediate to notice that once the symmetry with respect to the operation $z \rightarrow -z$, an unbalance among the loss functions $\Gamma_{\ell=+1}$ and $\Gamma_{\ell=-1}$ appear, while these two quantities turn out to be coincident for the symmetric structure shown in Figure 5.1a. Therefore, OAM resolved EELS turns out to be an appropriate technique to experimentally probe the presence or the absence of this type of symmetry for the plasmonic nanostructure under consideration.

This property of chiral nanostructures has been already analysed in [13Error! Bookmark not defined.], in the case of chiral assemblies of metallic nanoparticles, which are expected to provide values for the dichroic function, defined as

$$D_{|\ell|}(E) = 100 \cdot \frac{\Gamma_{+\ell}(E) - \Gamma_{-\ell}(E)}{\Gamma_{+\ell}(E) + \Gamma_{-\ell}(E)} \quad (7.5)$$

of the order of 10-15%. In the following, we present simulations performed for a metallic nanostructure which should exhibit giant electron dichroism, i.e values of $D_{|\ell|}(E)$ (for $|\ell| = 1$) of

Figure 5.2 a) OAM resolved loss functions the structure shown in Figure 1.5a. b) OAM resolved loss functions the structure shown in Figure 1.5b. In both cases the probe is centered in correspondence of the crossing points among the two nanorods, as denoted by the red spots plotted on the top views of the two nanostructures.

the order of 100%, which could greatly simplify the experimental detection of this effect (already attempted in [14] for a cluster of nanospheres).

This structure is reported in Figure 5.3a and it is made of two identical open silver nanorings (embedded in vacuum), each of them characterized by a height of 10 nm, an external radius of 50 nm and an internal one of 25 nm; the spacing between the two nanorings is 20 nm and the opening angle has been fixed to 30° in all the calculations. The rings are rotated with respect to one another in order to break the mirror symmetry, as one can observe from the image.

Figure 5.3 a) Tilted view of the chiral plasmonic structure. b) Simulated OAM-resolved EEL spectra for the $\ell = +1$ (blue dashed line) and $\ell = -1$ (red line) components: notice the presence of a peak only for

$\ell = -1$ at 1.53 eV, which is responsible for a giant electron dichroism effect. c) 2D representation of the EEL spectra convoluted with a Gaussian function simulating the limited instrumental resolution ($\Delta E = 0.3\text{eV}$ and $\Delta\ell = 0.5\hbar$). It is immediate to observe, despite the experimental broadening, a very pronounced asymmetry between the signals for $\ell = +1$ and $\ell = -1$.

In Figure 5.3b, we show the energy loss spectra for $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = -1$, the functions $\Gamma_{+1}(E)$ and $\Gamma_{-1}(E)$ respectively, calculated for an incident Gaussian beam with a beam waist of 50 nm, centered in the common center of the two rings. The comparison of the spectra immediately shows strong differences, in particular at the energy $E' = 1.53\text{ eV}$ where the loss function $\Gamma_{-1}(E)$ is predominant while the opposite polarity $\Gamma_{+1}(E)$ is almost completely absent, leading to a dichroic signal $D_1(E)$ close to 100%, while a dichroic effect (even if much less pronounced) is also present in the peak at 2.17 eV. Conversely, the peak at $E'' = 2.03\text{ eV}$ is more intense for the $\ell = 1$ component even though the difference is only $D_1(E'') = 20\%$. A realistic experiment, simulated in Figure 3.5c), is also able to observe the dichroism: by comparing the two spectra for $\ell = +1$ and $\ell = -1$, one can readily notice the complete absence of the peak at 1.53 eV in the $\ell = 1$ spectrum and a strong asymmetry among the $\ell = +1$ and $\ell = -1$ spectra. It is interesting to understand the physical origin of this giant dichroism for the mode at about 1.53 eV. To do this we have performed an OAM decomposition similar to the one reported in Chapter 4, for this particular plasmon resonance: the coefficients C_m are reported in Figure 5.4, together with the surface charge distribution associate to this mode.

Figure 5.4 Coefficients C_m for the mode at $E = 1.53\text{ eV}$ for the chiral structure shown in Figure 3.5a: notice that only the coefficient C_{+1} turns out to be effectively not negligible.

From the decomposition coefficients plotted in Figure 5.4, it is simple to realize that the mode at $E = 1.53\text{ eV}$ (from now on called mode a) has only C_1 different from zero: therefore, the potential $\phi_a(x, y; q)$ can be approximated as

$$\phi_a(x, y; q) \approx f_a(r)e^{i\varphi}$$

And so, by direct substitution in the formula derived in Chapter 1 for Γ_ℓ , we explain why in the OAM resolved EEL spectra only a peak for Γ_{-1} is observed.

The fact that $\phi_a(x, y; q) \approx f_a(r)e^{i\varphi}$ can also be understood looking at the phase profile of the function $\phi_a(x, y; q)$ (which is complex once the mirror symmetry is lost): this is reported in Figure 5.5: notice that it is characterized by an on axis singularity, with topological charge equal to +1, i.e. the characteristic phase of a function $\phi_a(x, y; q) \approx f_a(r)e^{i\varphi}$, well known in electron and light optics.

Figure 5.5 In plane phase profile of the potential associated to the mode with excitation energy $E = 1.53$ eV.

6. NANOSTRUCTURE FABRICATION

The details of the plasmonic structure determine the features of the plasmon loss. A small structure produces small signal but highly blue shifted, so we aimed for the smallest structures as possible but this turned out to be a challenge for nanofabrication.

For this fabrication we used mainly two techniques namely EBL and He-ion microscopes since FIB is too broad.

Figure 6.1 Shows the 2 SEM images of plasmonic structures

EBL was used to register a pattern on PMMA resist that was used as template for plasmonic structures made of silver. Fig 6.1 shows a SEM image of two of the EBL plasmonic structures. The structures correspond to the design in fig 5.1 a and 4.6. It is possible to appreciate features as small as 10 nm and this demonstrates the level of precision of the technique.

We also used the He-Ion microscope as a sort of more precise FIB to construct the cylindrical plasmonic structure as in fig 2.2. For this work we evaporated silver on a membrane of SiN and removed the silver by the ion mill on a circular corona. The central cylinder in the center is silver is 40 nm in diameter.

Figure 6.2 SEM Image of the plasmonic structure based on a small cylinder (here visible in the center).

7. EARLY EXPERIMENTAL DATA ON PLASMONS

The data on the deliverable D2.6 indicate that we can already obtain a OAM spectrum. An example of OAM spectrum for a nominal superposition of $|L=-10\rangle$ and $|L=0\rangle$ is shown in the figure below .

Figure 7.1 Experimental example of OAM sorter with for a nominal superposition of $|L=-10\rangle$ and $|L=0\rangle$. The OAm dispersion is here vertical.

The image show two separate peaks with the OAM axis being in the vertical direction but the FWHM is still too large for any practical use in plasmon experiments.

The horizontal direction is instead the spectrum of the log-radial momentum operator $P_r = r \frac{\partial}{\partial r}$.

Still we want to show here how the setup of the microscope is being changed to obtain an OAM-ELS spectrum.

First of all we must notice that the image here is already obtained by the use of the GIF spectrometer. In fact the GIF can be used in both spectroscopy and imaging mode.

In imaging mode, if no slit is introduced the image is just a replica of the image obtained in the main screen but magnified (typically by a factor x10).

So even for normal imaging of the beam we take advantage of this extra magnification since the normal lens system is limited in this sense.

However our aim is to produce a spectrum with double dispersion in both OAM and ELS. In this case we must somehow disregard or integrate over P_r .

We consider now the plasmonic structure in fig 6.1 as an example to test plasmonic spectroscopy. Fig 6,2 shows the image of the sample as seen through the STEM probe. The convergence has been fixed to 2.5 mrad and the sample z position has been lifted until the probe appeared slightly larger than the sample.

Figure 7.2 Convergent TEM beam superimposed to the structure of interest.

Figure 7.3 OAM spectrum of the elastically imaged particles. The 3 fold symmetry produces a dominant $L=3n$ (n being an integer) contribution.

For such a sample the OAM sorter should give a typical spectrum with lines at $L=3n$ (n being an integer) as indicated in fig 7.3. while the spectrum should be composed of $L=0,1,2,3 \hbar$ (dominantly $1,2 \hbar$) as in fig 4.3. Therefore we should see peaks in different place between elastic and inelastic scattering.

The first and most obvious way to account for this is to use the EFTEM mode and acquire energy filtered images at different energies in the range [0 -4 eV].

We select a single energy window and form image only with those electrons. Two relevant example at different energies are shown in fig 7.4.

Figure 7.4 Filtered image for $E=0$ and $E=2.2$ eV.

Clearly the images are very noisy and the result are of different interpretation. While the stretched one is most probably $L=0$ it is difficult to interpret the presence of only one extra peak whose position can be roughly found at $L=6 \hbar$.

We believe that some problem in the GIF and the sorter hampers a correct OAM analysis

Nevertheless we will make a test of the possible hardware configuration.

Figure 7.5 OAM vs energy loss based on the set of images like in fig 7,3.

In this case images have been acquired with a step of 0.4 eV ad a nominal slit aperture of 2eV.

Each image has been integrated in the P_r direction and the images have been composed to form a pseudo-spectrum shown in figure. The OAM spectrum features two main peaks that are those in fig 7.4. The peaks are reproduced in the pseudo-spectrum at all energies.

Considering the noise level and the uncertainties we cannot draw any conclusion at the moment.

Another possibility is to use the spectroscopy mode to create a 2D spectrum directly. In this case the ELS dispersion direction is put orthogonal to the OAM direction. In this way the P_r dispersion, appropriately de-magnified, is superimposed to the energy dispersion.

Unfortunately to produce this kind of setup for the filter requires an appropriate tuning of the spectrometer that need to be separately operated by Gatan.

In fact what we can observe in image below two example of 2D spectra OAM –EL spectra

Figure 7.5 Example of OAM (vertical) and energy loss (horizontal) spectrum containing the signature of volume plasmon.

The energy dispersion is in this case horizontal while the OAM is the vertical direction.

Unfortunately the image is saturated and is characterized by a terrible Point spread function in the vertical direction. In fact in order to increase the magnification in the y direction we acted on the vertical quadrupoles of the filter but this was accompanied but a defocus and blurring of the image.

Still the image shows one of the correct features we expect the Volume plasmon of SiN (of no direct interest in our analysis) is well visible at an energy of about 20 eV (here indicated by a tick in the horizontal scale). Except for the spreading effect in OAM this peak is concentrated to the $L=0$ axis in y as we expect for this peak as it should not get almost any OAM feature.

Finally for comparison we show in the image below the dispersion in spectral mode without magnification in the vertical direction. The OAM spectrum of the superposition beam of $|L=-10\rangle$ and $|L=0\rangle$ is here comprised of only two very close-by line.

Figure 7.6 Example of OAM (vertical) and energy loss (horizontal) spectrum with only elastic signal as in fig 7.1

8. CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable we have demonstrated how the dispersion in OAM of electrons inelastically scattered by localized surface plasmons in metallic nanostructures could give access to information not directly available in conventional STEM EELS experiments: for example mode recognition according to their azimuthal symmetry or clarification of the hybridization mechanisms which occur once an initial plasmonic nanostructure is deformed.

In Chapter 4 we have presented a series of numerical examples in which the adoption of OAM resolved EELS could permit to resolve plasmonic resonances with separation in energy smaller than the energetic resolution available experimentally: this is possible as the different modes give maxima for OAM resolved loss functions associated to different values of l .

We have discussed the capability of this technique to probe the presence or the absence of mirror symmetry with respect to the xy plane of a given plasmonic nanostructure; further we have also proposed a composite system which is expected to exhibit giant electron dichroism and so which could be a good candidate for a first experimental demonstration of this effect.

Future work on this field will concern the realization of experiments on OAM resolved EELS on metallic nanostructure and the attempt, from the theoretical point of view, to extend the formalism exposed here in a quasi-static framework to a fully retarded regime, in order to obtain simulations in better quantitative agreement with those expected experimentally.

The section 7 in particular shows the potentiality and the limits of the present configuration and we hope we can improve these results with technical improvements.

ANNEX 1: REVIEWERS

Rev1: This work looks pretty accurate and full of insight into plasmonic world. I really hope that the final experiment can be done. In facts I appreciate that you put suggestions on the way experimental problems like resolution affect your results.

I have then 2 questions:

- What happens if we cannot get an OAM resolution better than $2\hbar$?
- In which way is this better than normal EELS scanning the beam?

We really hope we can get a better OAM resolution in the future experiments working on a detailed tuning of the electrostatic sorter should solve the problem, $1\hbar$ should be reachable according to previous deliverable. In any case in the deliverable we tried to search for large OAM signatures in plasmon loss.

This technique gives potentially the same results as scanning, but it is somehow clearer because 1) the symmetry of the modes is often more clear by the OAM analysis, 2) it is logically more meaningful to excite always the same set of states and then analyze the

symmetry of them rather than changing them all the time. Since there is an inelastic scattering the time inversion does not hold and the two operation are not equivalent.

Moreover we start to see that in the analyses of organic molecule (beyond the present aim of the project) this can be a winning strategy as there will be no need to scan inside the molecule.

Rev2: This is a very interesting work and I am happy I participated to the measurements. The interpretation of the data still seems to be strange.

We agree with you, with the new version of the deliverable we hope we will be able to show a better and more reliable ELS OAM spectrum. Still if you consider this is the first time such a device is working the results are still considerable.

I corrected several typos and propose to put a title for each chapter

Done thank you.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL

ANNEX 3 - REFERENCES

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